

GEOCHEMICAL AND MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF ISHARA SANDSTONE DEPOSIT, SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

A total number of eleven [11] sandstone samples were collected at Ishara Remo in Ogun state in order to classify the deposit of the Ise Formation as exposed in this area on the bases of its chemical and mineralogical make-up. Out of these, nine [9] samples were selected for both geochemical and petrographic studies. Relative concentration of the major oxide groups – silica and alumina alkali oxides, iron oxide and magnesia has been used to classify the deposit. The result of the geochemical analysis on the selected samples shows that the classification agrees with parameters of $\log \text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 < 1.5$ and either of $\log \text{K}_2\text{O} / \text{Na}_2\text{O}$ or $\log \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO} / \text{Na}_2\text{O} = 0$. On the basis of these, the sandstone could be classified as sub-greywacke or rather low rank greywacke. The ratio of the alkali $[\text{Na}_2\text{O} / \text{K}_2\text{O}] > 0$ also shows that the sandstone deposit is immature. Moreover, quartz, feldspar and rock fragments were microscopically identified with quartz constituting less than 90% of the total mineral constituent, while feldspar constitutes less than 25% and rock fragments make up more than 15%. On the basis of this also, the deposit can equally be classified as greywacke.

KEYWORDS: Sandstone, Greywacke, Lithostratigraphic, Geochemical, Mineralogical and Petrological.

INTRODUCTION

Sedimentary rocks are classified generally based on texture, cement, and groups. These groups can be subdivided into three: detrital / clastic, biogenic and chemical sediments. Sediments belong to the clastic group, which could be clean having silica cement, matrix rich-greywacke and the arkosic type.

The Dahomeyan is an extensive sedimentary basin extending almost from south-Ghana to Benin (precisely the Benin hinge-line). The Dahomey basin (Fig.1) is a marginal pull-apart basin (Klemme, 1975) or Margin sag basin (Kingston et al., 1983), which was initiated during the early Cretaceous separation of African and South American lithospheric plates.

Geology and stratigraphy of the basin has been described by various workers: Jones and Hockey, 1964; Omatsola and Adegoke, 1980; Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981; Agagu, 1985; Elueze and Nton, 2004; Akinmosin, 2005. In most parts of the basin, the stratigraphy is dominated by sand and shale alternations with minor proportion of limestone, [Agagu, 1985]. In all, eight lithostratigraphic units have been identified and described by these workers.

The present work was carried out in Ishara, Ogun state, southwestern Nigeria. It is a transition zone between sedimentary and basement complex lying between latitudes $6^{\circ}57'1$ and $6^{\circ}59'1$ N; and longitudes $3^{\circ}39'1$ and $3^{\circ}41'1$ E (Fig. 2). This study intends to classify the sandstone deposit of Ise Formation (oldest lithostratigraphic unit of the Dahomey basin) as exposed in this area on the bases of its chemical and mineralogical make-up.

STRATIGRAPHY.

The reviewed work of Omatsola and Adegoke (1981) on the Cretaceous stratigraphy of the Dahomey basin has recognized three formations belonging to the Abeokuta group. These are: the Ise Formation, consisting essentially of continental sands, grits and siltstones, overlying the basement complex. Neocomian to Albian age has been assigned to this Formation. Overlying the Ise Formation is the Afowo Formation, which consists of

FIG.1: East-West geological section showing the Dahomey Basin and upper part of the Niger Delta (After Whiteman, 1982).

course to medium-grained sandstones with variable interbeds of shales, siltstones and clay. The sediments of this formation were deposited in a transitional to marginal marine environment turonian to Maastrichtian age has been assigned to this formation. The araromi formation consists essentially of sand, overlain by dark-grey shales and interbedded limestone and marls occasional lignite bands. The formation conformably overlies the Afowo Formation and Maastrichtian to Paleocene age has been assigned (Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981).

Overlying the Abeokuta group conformably is the imo group, which comprises of shale limestone and marls. The two-lithostratigraphic units under this group are: Ewekoro formation consists of thick fossiliferous limestone. Adegoke (1977) described the formation as consisting of shaly limestone 12.5m thick which tends to be sandy and divided it into three microfacies. Ogbe (1972) further modified this and proposed a fourth unit. It is Paleocene in age and associated with shallow marine environment due to abundance of coralline algae, gastropods, pelecypods, echinoid fragments and other skeletal debris. Akinbo Formation lies on the Ewekoro Formation and it comprises of shale, glauconitic rock bank, and gritty sand to pure grey and with little clay. Lenses of limestone from Ewekoro formation grades literally into the Akinbo shale very close to the base. The base is characterized by the presence of a glauconitic rock. The age of the formation is Paleocene to Eocene.

Overlying the Imo group is the Oshoshun formation. It is a sequence of mostly pale greenish-grey laminated phosphatic marls, light grey white-purple clay with interbeds of sandstones. It also consists of claystone underlain by argillaceous limestone of phosphatic and glauconitic materials in the lower part of the formation are Eocene in age (Agagu, 1985). The sedimentation of the Oshoshun Formation was followed by a regression, which deposited the sandstone unit of Ilaro Formation (Kogbe, 1976). The sequence represents mainly coarse sandy estuarine deltaic and continental beds, which show rapid lateral facies change.

The coastal plain sands are the youngest sedimentary unit in the eastern Dahomey basin. It probably overlay the Ilaro Formation unconformably, but convincing evidence as to this is lacking (Jones and Hockey, 1964). It consists of soft, poorly sorted clayey sand and pebbly sands. The age is from Oligocene to Recent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total number of eleven sandstone samples were collected at different locations from exposed Ishara sandstone deposits. Out of these samples, nine were systematically selected for laboratory analyses. They were first disaggregated cautiously to preserve the grain shapes and later subjected to mineralogical and chemical analyses.

The mineralogical analysis was carried out petrographically with the prepared thin sections viewed under both

polarized and crossed nicols. The proportion of the mineral composition of each sample was estimated in percentage.

X-ray fluorescence [XRF] analysis was later carried out on the nine [9] selected samples for their major oxides composition (Fairchild *et al*, 1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Geochemical Analysis

Result of the geochemical analysis carried out the analysed samples is presented in Table 1. The concentration of three major oxide groups has been used to classify sandstones: silica and alumina, alkali oxides, and iron oxide plus magnesia. The enrichment of SiO₂ over Al₂O₃ by mechanical and chemical process produces quartz arenites [orthoquartzites]. Silica [quartz] enrichment is a measure of sandstone maturity, and is a reflection of the duration and intensity of weathering and destruction of other minerals during transportation. Abundant alkalis [Na₂O and K₂O] characterize immature sandstones such as arkoses and greywacke. The ratio of Na₂O is determined by the sum of provenance and diagenesis.

The following are the parameters for the classification of sandstone based on chemical approach. They are used according to Blatt and others, 1972; Herron, 1988; Pettijohn and others, 1972; and Potter, 1978:

- i. When $\log \text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 1.5$, such sandstone is termed arenites.
- ii. When $\log \text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 < 1$ and $\log(\text{K}_2\text{O} / \text{Na}_2\text{O}) < 0$, it is termed greywacke
- iii. When $\log(\text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3) < 1.5$, $\log(\text{K}_2\text{O} / \text{Na}_2\text{O}) > 0$ and $\log(\text{Fe}_T\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO}) / (\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O})$, it is termed an Arkose.
- iv. When $\log(\text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3) < 1.5$ and either $\log([\text{K}_2\text{O} / \text{Na}_2\text{O}) < 0$ or $\log(\text{Fe}_T\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO} / \text{K}_2\text{O} / \text{Na}_2\text{O}) > 0$, it is termed to be lithic arenite (including sub-greywacke and protoquartzites).

Based on the above parameters, the ratio of the oxides of each analyzed sample has the following results:

For example:

i. In sample A-

$$\text{Log SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.4992.$$

$$\text{Log K}_2\text{O}/\text{Na}_2\text{O} = 0.22.$$

$$\text{Log Fe}_T\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO}/\text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{Na}_2\text{O} = 0.075$$

ii. In sample C –

$$\text{Log SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.89.$$

Log K₂O/Na₂O = 0.20.

Log Fe_TO₃ + MgO/K₂O + Na₂O = 0.20.

iii. In sample E -

Log SiO₂/Al₂O₃ = 1.25.

Log K₂O/Na₂O = 0.20.

Log Fe_TO₃ + MgO/K₂O + Na₂O = 0.13.

iv. In sample G -

Log SiO₂/Al₂O₃ = 1.27.

Log Na₂O/K₂O = 0.20.

Log Fe_TO₃ + MgO/Na₂ + K₂O = 0.21.

TABLE 1: GEOCHEMICAL RESULT OF THE ANALYZED SAMPLES.

	SAMPLE A	SAMPLE B	SAMPLE C	SAMPLE D	SAMPLE E	SAMPLE F	SAMPLE G	SAMPLE H	SAMPLE I
SiO ₂	72.89	82.65	81.72	81.75	81.72	83.09	85.52	83.25	73.19
Al ₂ O ₃	23.09	9.90	10.62	10.40	4.54	7.80	4.50	7.85	22.30
K ₂ O	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.10
Na ₂ O	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.06
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
MgO	0.00	0.19	0.14	0.15	0.21	0.20	0.21	0.18	0.00
FeO	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.08
CaO	3.54	2.75	2.90	2.85	2.90	2.79	2.74	2.76	3.61
TiO ₂	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.06
SO ₃	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.00

MINERALOGICAL ANALYSIS

The following range of classification was used according to Klein, 1963; McBride, 1963; Okada, 1971; Pettijohn, Potter and Siever, 1972. This classification takes three major components into consideration, which are quartz, feldspar, and rock fragments. The following are the parameters for mineralogical classification:

- i When quartz is greater than 90%, it is termed Quartz arenites.
- ii When feldspar constituent is greater than 25%, it is termed Arkose.
- iii When the fine-grained matrix is greater than 15%, it is termed Greywacke.

The prepared sections were viewed under the petrological microscope, it was observed that the sandstones are poorly sorted with very fine grained matrix (almost opaque under polarized light), see Plates 1 and 2. Based on this study, it was found out that the quartz percentage is less than 90%, and also the proportion of feldspar is less than 25%. Consequent upon this, the sandstone can be said to belong to the class of greywacke having matrix proportion greater than 15% [Folk, 1974] and [Pettijohn, 1975].

CONCLUSIONS

Result of the above studies indicate that the sandstone has matrix proportion of greater than 15%, hence mineralogically, it can be classified as greywacke. Moreover, values of less than 1 and greater than 1 were obtained for the ratios of $\log \text{SiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\log \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{MgO} / \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$ respectively. The sandstone deposit can equally be classified as sub-greywacke or low rank greywacke from geochemical point of view.

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PLATE 1: A PHOTOMICROGRAPH OF ISHARA SANDSTONE SHOWING THE SAND-SIZE FRAMEWORK AND THE FINE-GRAINED MATRIX.

PLATE 2: A PHOTOMICROGRAPH OF ISHARA SANDSTONE UNDER POLARIZED LIGHT.